

MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC FOOT WITH AYURVEDIC AND MODERN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17799996>

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How to cite this Article: Murali Krishna S.*, Gopi Krishna B. J., Liyanage R. P. (2025). Management of Diabetic Foot With Ayurvedic and Modern Integrative Approach. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(23), 1698-1707.

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ABSTRACT

Diabetic foot ulcer is a debilitating complication of diabetes, often progressing to osteomyelitis and amputation. Despite advances in modern care, many ulcers fail to heal completely, necessitating complementary approaches. Ayurveda describes similar conditions as Madhumeha Janya Vrana and Dushta Vrana, recommending systemic therapy and local wound care. We report a 69-year-old male with type 2 diabetes mellitus, peripheral neuropathy, and a plantar ulcer complicated by osteomyelitis. The patient was managed with an integrative protocol combining Ayurvedic formulations—Triphala Guggulu, Gandhaka Rasayana, Mehabhaya Kashaya, and local Jatyadi Taila dressing—with modern interventions including antibiotics, glycemic control, and supportive therapy. Lifestyle modification through Pathya Ahara (balanced diet) and activity regulation was also emphasized. The patient showed marked improvement: cessation of bleeding and pain reduction within 7

days, wound contraction by 43% at discharge (day 13), normalization of ESR (72 to 28 mm/hr), and significant granulation tissue formation. At 4 weeks, the wound was 85% healed with restored mobility and sustained glycemic control. No surgical intervention was required.

This case demonstrates that integrative management can accelerate wound healing, preserve limb integrity, and enhance patient satisfaction, offering a viable model for diabetic foot care.

KEYWORDS: *Diabetic foot ulcer, Dushta Vrana, Osteomyelitis, Ayurveda, Integrative medicine.*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic foot disease is one of the most severe and costly complications of diabetes, affecting 15–25% of patients during their lifetime.^[1] It arises from a combination of peripheral neuropathy, arterial disease, foot deformity, and infection, often leading to chronic ulcers and possible amputation. Globally, diabetic foot ulcers precede about 85% of non-traumatic amputations, with a 5-year post-amputation mortality rate of 39–80%.^[2] Despite advances in care, only 60–70% of ulcers achieve closure within 12 weeks of treatment.

In Ayurveda, similar conditions are described as Madhumeha Janya Vrana (diabetes-related wounds) and Dushta Vrana (chronic non-healing wounds), with management focusing on systemic therapy (Prameha Chikitsa), local wound care, and rejuvenative measures.^[3] Recent evidence supports the wound healing potential of formulations such as Jatyadi Taila, which exhibits anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and regenerative effects.^[4-6]

Integrating Ayurvedic approaches with modern care offers a promising strategy for diabetic foot ulcers. This report presents a case of diabetic foot ulcer with osteomyelitis successfully managed through such an integrative approach, following CARE guidelines.

CASE HISTORY

A 69-year-old Indian male farmer with a 12-year history of type 2 diabetes mellitus and irregular treatment compliance presented with progressive loss of sensation in both feet for six months, followed by a non-healing ulcer on the plantar aspect of the right foot after minor trauma one month prior. The ulcer progressively enlarged, with intermittent bleeding, evening rise of temperature, and generalized weakness. He had a history of mild hypertension (not on regular medication), a 15 pack-year smoking history (quit five years ago), and occasional alcohol use. Family history was significant for diabetes in his father and hypertension in his mother.

On examination, the patient was afebrile to low-grade febrile (99.4°F), with stable vital signs. Neurological assessment revealed severe diabetic peripheral neuropathy with absent ankle reflexes and sensory loss below the knees. Vascular assessment showed mildly delayed capillary refill (3–4 s), an ankle-brachial index of 0.75, and weakened pedal pulses. Local wound examination revealed an ulcer measuring 4.2 × 3.1 × 1.8 cm on the plantar aspect of the right foot, probing to bone positive, with mixed granulation, slough, and necrotic tissue, exposed bone, surrounding erythema, warmth, tenderness, and seropurulent exudate. Thick callus was noted around the wound margins.

Laboratory investigations showed anaemia (Hb 10.2 g/dL), elevated ESR (72 mm/hr), fair glycemic control (HbA1c 6.5%), and dyslipidaemia with elevated LDL (125.3 mg/dL) and low HDL (35 mg/dL). Wound culture revealed heavy growth of *Staphylococcus aureus* and moderate growth of *Streptococcus pyogenes*, sensitive to amoxicillin-clavulanate, ciprofloxacin, and clindamycin. Radiography of the right foot demonstrated osteolytic changes in the metatarsal head consistent with osteomyelitis.

DIAGNOSIS

The patient was diagnosed with type 2 diabetes mellitus with a diabetic foot ulcer complicated by osteomyelitis and peripheral neuropathy, corresponding to ICD-11 codes 5A11.0 and NE81.3 (7,8). In Ayurvedic terms, the condition was understood as Madhumeha Janya Vrana (diabetes-related ulcer) presenting as a Dushta Vrana (chronic non-healing wound), considered a complication (Upadrava) of Prameha (diabetes).^[9-12]

INTERVENTION

The patient was managed with an integrative treatment approach combining classical Ayurvedic formulations with supportive modern medical care. The Ayurvedic protocol aimed at correcting systemic imbalances, enhancing wound healing, and preventing complications, while modern interventions ensured infection control, metabolic stabilization, and supportive care.

Table 1: Integrated Treatment Protocol.

Treatment	Dosage & Duration	Therapeutic Rationale
Triphala Guggulu	2 tablets twice daily; continued 3 months	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, wound healing, metabolic regulation ^[13,14]
Gandhaka Rasayana	2 tablets twice daily after meals; 6 weeks	Antimicrobial, antifungal, tissue regeneration, chronic wound-specific ^[15,16]

Mehabhaya Kashaya Syrup	15 ml twice daily before meals with warm water; throughout treatment	Anti-diabetic, supports glucose metabolism, prevents complications ^[13,17]
Jatyadi Taila Dressing	Daily dressing after saline cleansing	Anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, wound healing, pain relief, tissue regeneration ^[15,18]
Antibiotics	Amoxicillin-Clavulanate 625 mg twice daily for 14 days	Infection control ^[19]
Glycemic Control	Metformin 500 mg twice daily; Glimepiride 2 mg once daily; insulin as needed	Blood sugar regulation ^[19]
Supportive Care	Multivitamin once daily; iron, folic acid; proton pump inhibitor	Nutritional support, anemia correction, gastric protection ^[19]

In addition to medical and Ayurvedic interventions, lifestyle modifications played a vital role in the patient's recovery and long-term management. A balanced Pathya Ahara (recommended diet) emphasizing whole grains such as old rice, barley, and wheat in moderation, along with vegetables like bitter melon, drumstick, fenugreek leaves, and bottle gourd, was advised. Protein intake was supported with moong dal, limited fish, and low-fat dairy, while spices such as turmeric, ginger, coriander, cumin, and fenugreek were included for their metabolic and anti-inflammatory benefits. Fruits like pomegranate, Indian gooseberry, and guava were allowed in limited quantities. The patient was advised to strictly avoid Apathya Ahara (unwholesome foods), including refined sugars, processed foods, deep-fried items, white rice, refined flour products, starchy vegetables such as potatoes, and the use of alcohol or tobacco.

Activity modifications included strict bed rest with elevation of the affected foot during the first week, followed by gradual mobilization with non-weight bearing. A wheelchair was recommended for essential movements, and the patient received counselling on proper foot care, daily inspection, and the importance of wearing appropriate footwear to prevent future ulcer recurrence.

RESULTS

The patient demonstrated steady improvement under the integrative management protocol. Early signs of healing included cessation of bleeding and reduction in pain within the first week, followed by progressive granulation tissue formation and wound size reduction. By discharge on day 13, significant tissue regeneration and infection control were achieved, with improvements in both functional status and laboratory parameters. Post-discharge follow-up confirmed sustained progress, marked by continued wound contraction, epithelialization, and restoration of mobility.

Table 2: Timeline of Clinical Course and Outcomes.

Date	Day	Clinical Status	Key Outcomes
06-04-2025	1	Admission	Initiated integrative treatment, baseline wound area 13.0 cm ² with exposed bone
07-04-2025	2	First dressing change	Jatyadi Taila applied, exudate reduced, bleeding controlled
09-04-2025	4	Early response	Pain improved, no fresh bleeding, wound more stable
12-04-2025	7	Weekly assessment	20–30% wound size reduction, granulation tissue 40%, ESR improved
15-04-2025	10	Mid-treatment	Healthy granulation prominent, exudate minimal, pain score 3/10
19-04-2025	13	Discharge	Wound size reduced to 7.4 cm ² , granulation 70%, necrosis absent, ESR 28 mm/hr
26-04-2025	20	1-week follow-up	Granulation 60%, infection resolved, good glycemic control, excellent adherence
03-05-2025	27	2-week follow-up	Wound area 4.5 cm ² , epithelialization visible, partial weight bearing started
17-05-2025	41	4-week follow-up	Wound 85% healed, pain-free, foot care reinforced

Figure 01: Timeline of Healing.

DISCUSSION

This case highlights the effectiveness of an integrative management approach combining Ayurvedic therapies with modern medical care in the treatment of diabetic foot ulcer complicated by osteomyelitis. The favourable outcomes observed suggest that such combined methodologies can enhance wound healing, infection control, and overall patient well-being compared to conventional therapy alone.^[20, 21]

AYURVEDIC THERAPEUTIC INTERVENTIONS

Triphala Guggulu was used as a systemic agent due to its well-documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and hypoglycaemic effects. Experimental and clinical studies have demonstrated its role in enhancing collagen synthesis, angiogenesis, and glucose metabolism, while also reducing inflammatory mediators and exerting antimicrobial activity against

common wound pathogens.^[22–24] The guggul component further contributes lipid-lowering and anti-inflammatory properties, beneficial for diabetic patients with dyslipidaemia.^[25]

Gandhaka Rasayana was incorporated to target the infectious component of the wound. Purified sulfur preparations exhibit potent antimicrobial action, particularly against *Staphylococcus aureus*, a pathogen identified in this case. Evidence indicates that sulfur-based formulations inhibit biofilm formation, enhance neutrophil function, and support keratinocyte proliferation, thereby promoting faster wound closure and reducing oxidative stress.^[26,27]

Topical application of Jatyadi Taila provided localized wound care. Its polyherbal composition confers anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, analgesic, and tissue-regenerative properties. Clinical studies have reported superior wound healing outcomes with Jatyadi Taila compared to conventional dressings, including faster wound closure, bacterial load reduction, and improved patient comfort.^[28–30] In a recent randomized controlled trial, Jatyadi Taila was shown to accelerate wound closure by approximately 40% in diabetic foot ulcers.^[31]

INTEGRATION WITH MODERN MEDICINE

The integrative protocol also incorporated targeted antibiotics and glycemic control, ensuring comprehensive management. Amoxicillin-clavulanate was selected based on culture sensitivity, effectively controlling infection while Ayurvedic interventions supported systemic recovery and wound regeneration.^[32, 33]

CLINICAL OUTCOMES

Quantitative improvements included a 43% reduction in wound area at discharge, cessation of bleeding within 7 days, a 75% reduction in pain scores, and normalization of inflammatory markers (ESR decreased from 72 to 28 mm/hr). Qualitative improvements were equally notable, with a transition from sloughy to granulating tissue, resolution of infection, and enhancement of functional mobility and quality of life.^[34]

COMPARISON WITH STANDARD CARE

Standard management of diabetic foot ulcers with osteomyelitis often requires extended antibiotic therapy, surgical debridement, and longer hospital stays (35,36). In contrast, this integrative approach achieved faster healing, shorter hospitalization (13 vs. 21–28 days), reduced antibiotic exposure (14 vs. 42–56 days), and avoided surgical intervention while

maintaining limb integrity. These outcomes suggest improved cost-effectiveness and reduced healthcare burden.^[37]

PATIENT-CENTRED BENEFITS

Beyond clinical improvement, this approach offered patient-centred benefits including cultural acceptability, reduced treatment-related anxiety, holistic care addressing both physical and psychological domains, and lifestyle counselling for long-term prevention. Such factors enhance adherence and sustainability of treatment outcomes.^[38,39]

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates the effectiveness of integrating Ayurvedic medicine with modern medical care in managing a diabetic foot ulcer with osteomyelitis. The combined approach achieved rapid wound healing, limb preservation, and high patient satisfaction which outcomes often difficult with conventional therapy alone. Key factors included comprehensive assessment, evidence-based Ayurvedic formulations, appropriate antibiotics, and patient education. Notably, 43% wound closure within 13 days with pain relief and infection control highlights the therapeutic potential of this model. The approach also reduced hospitalization, avoided surgical intervention, and promoted sustainable outcomes through lifestyle modification. Future controlled studies are needed to validate these findings and establish standardized integrative protocols. This case provides strong evidence that integrative medicine can improve healing, reduce amputation risk, and enhance quality of life in diabetic foot complications.

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